

Table 2: Effect of First meal of the Day on Glycemia in healthy individuals and subjects at high risk for developing or with type 2 diabetes

Study	Health status Age (years) BMI (kg/m ²)	Duration & design of dietary intervention	Sample size	Description of groups	Dietary intervention	Selected clinical outcomes
Effect of first meal of the day on glycemia						
• Breakfast skipping or consuming						
Morris, <i>et al.</i> , 2015 [116]	Healthy 28±9 25.4±2.6	2 weeks Within-participant cross-over	14	Circadian alignment Circadian misalignment (12h shift)	Alignment protocol had B at 8:00 AM Misalignment protocol had “B” at 8:00 PM Isocaloric diets of 15–20% PRO, 45–50% CHO, 30–35% FAT	+8% and +14% ppd AUC _{Glu} and ppd AUC _{Ins} at Dinner time +3% ISR at Dinner time +12% and -27% ppd AUC _{Glu} and ppd AUC _{Ins} in biological evening +8% ISR in biological evening -21% Fasting Ins in biological evening +14% and +9% late phase Ins/ISR and 24h Ins at circadian misalignment
Betts, <i>et al.</i> , 2014 [133]	Healthy lean 36±11 22.4±2.2	6 weeks Randomized controlled trial	33	B group Fasting group	B: ≥700 kcal before 11:00, Fasting group: extend o/n fast until 12:00, <i>ad libitum</i> intake for the rest of the day	Glu (mg/dL) +1.3 (fast) vs +1.1 (B) Ins (μIU/mL) +0.32 (fast) vs +0.35 (B) HOMA-IR +0.10 (fast) vs +0.10 (B) C-ISI Matsuda index +0.38 (fast) vs -0.97 (B) Index of adipose insulin sensitivity (%) +3.3 (fast) vs +9.9 (B) Peak Glu until 12:00 + 1.1 mmol/L in B vs fasting Mean morning Glu +0.3 mmol/L in B vs fasting Greater Glu variability in fasting group
Chowdhury, <i>et al.</i> , 2016 [136]	Obese 44±10 33.7±4.9	6 weeks Randomized controlled trial	23	B group Fasting group	B: ≥700 kcal before 11:00, Fasting group: extend o/n fast until 12:00,	Fasting Glu (mg/dL) +1.7 (fast) vs +1.4 (B) Fasting Ins (μIU/mL) -0.62 (fast) vs +0.39 (B) HOMA-IR -0.13 (fast) vs +0.18 (B) C-ISI Matsuda index -0.05 (fast) vs +0.05 (B) Ins AUC Glu, mg•120 min/dL +171 (fast) vs -231 (B)

					<i>ad libitum</i> intake for the rest of the day	
Jakubowicz, <i>et al.</i> , 2015 [138]	T2D 56.9±1.0 28.2±0.6	2 test days Randomized, open-label, crossover-within-subject clinical trial	22	YesB (B, L, D) NoB (L, D)	Each test meal: 701±8 kcal; 26% PRO, 54% CHO, 20% FAT, 7% fiber B at 8:00h, L at 13:30h, D at 19:00h	<u>NoB vs YesB after B</u> : Glu (mg/dL•min) -43%, Ins (μIU/mL•min) -72.1%, Glucagon (pg/mL•min) -20.6% C-peptide (ng/ml•min) -63.3%, iGLP-1 (pmol/L•min) -60.5% <u>NoB vs YesB after L</u> : Glu (mg/dL•min) +39.8%, Ins (μIU/mL•min) -24.7%, Glucagon (pg/mL•min) +9.7% C-peptide (ng/ml•min) -13.6%, iGLP-1 (pmol/L•min) -21.5% <u>NoB vs YesB after D</u> : Glu (mg/dL•min) +24.9%, Ins (μIU/mL•min) -10.8%, Glucagon (pg/mL•min) +8.5% C-peptide (ng/ml•min) -14.5%, iGLP-1 (pmol/L•min) -14.5%
Jakubowicz, <i>et al.</i> , 2017 [139]	<u>Healthy</u> : 44.3±2.9 23.1±0.4 <u>T2D</u> : 66.8±1.9 30.7±1.1	2 test days Randomized open-label crossover-within-subject clinical trial	32	YesB NoB	Each test meal: 572±8 kcal 32% PRO 49% CHO 19.4% FAT	+15-18% AUC _{Glu} after lunch w/o B -25% AUC _{Ins} after L for T2D grp w/o B -35% AUC _{iGLP-1} after L on NoB
Nas, <i>et al.</i> , 2017 [140]	Healthy adults 24.6±3.3 23.7±4.6	3 test days Randomized crossover nutritional intervention	17	Control (C) (3 meals) BSD (B skipping) DSD (D skipping)	Isocaloric diets 55% CHO, 30% FAT, 15% PRO BSD-washout-C-DSD or DSD-washout-C-BSD	HOMA-IR 1.96±0.82 (C), 2.07±0.91 (BSD), 1.96±1.05 (DSD) Glycemia _{tAUC} (mg/dLx24h): 2360±111 (C), 2425±131 (BSD), 2374±165 (DSD) MAGE 3.90±1.32 (C), 3.65±1.52 (BSD), 3.28±1.75 (DSD) C-peptide (μg/d) 74±38 (C), 86±40 (BSD), 75±42 (DSD) iAUC _{Ins} (μU/mLx 2h) after L: 211±74 (BSD) 144±74 (DSD)

						iAUC _{Glu} (mg/dLx 2h) after L: 114±41 (BSD), 62±40 (DSD) HOMA-IR pp after L: 59±44 (BSD), 27±23 (DSD)
Kobayashi, <i>et al.</i> , 2014 [141]	Healthy 25.3±1.2 BW 74.5±4.3 kg (noB), 73.9±4.2 kg (B)	2 test days Randomized crossover	8	B (3 meals) noB (2 meals)	PRO 364±16 kcal CHO 1310±77 kcal FAT 462±33 kcal Individually adjusted meals of 2190±124 kcal/day B at 8:00h, L at 12:00h, D at 19:00	+9 mg/dl Blood Glu after L in noB vs B group (P<0.05) +10 mg/dl sleep Blood Glu in noB vs B group (P<0.05) AUC _{Glu} after L 409±99 mg/dl min in B group vs 811±101 mg/dl min in noB group AUC _{Glu} after D 1049±144 mg/dl min in B group vs 1196±204 mg/dl min in noB group

• **Breakfast composition**

Rosi, <i>et al.</i> , 2018 [135]	Healthy 24±2 23.4±1.6	7 weeks Randomized, crossover, and controlled trial	15	F-CTRL BR-BREAD BR-MUESLI BR-RICE	Energy-free meal with a cup of decaf coffee (~fasting) 3 isoenergetic meals with similar PRO: with a cup of semi-skimmed milk, an apple, and cereal foods as indicated below: White bread with chocolate hazelnut spread, GI<55, GL~22	The RICE group had significantly higher: - AUC _{Ins} 120mins after B - AUC _{Glu} 120mins after B - Plasma Glu after B
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Kang, <i>et al.</i> , 2013 [144]	Subjects with impaired (IGR) and normal (NGR) Glu regulation 46.4±13.8 18.5-24.9	3 days Cross-sectional study	133	LC (low CHO) MC (medium CHO) HC (high CHO)	<p>Diet of 30 kcal/kg/day calorie intake from three daily meals According to CHO in B: Low-carbohydrate (LC) meal with < 45% CHO</p> <p>Medium-carbohydrate (MC) meal with CHO between 45% and 65% High-carbohydrate (HC) meal with > 65% CHO</p>	In subjects with impaired Glu regulation: Significantly ↑ ppd Glu, Glu peak, Glu excursion, and iAUC _{GLU} in subjects with impaired Glu regulation after B with >50% CHO
Jakubowicz, <i>et al.</i> , 2017 [151]	T2D 59.0±0.7 32.11±0.1	12 weeks Randomized, open-label,	48	42g total PRO: WBdiet (whey, 28g)	At B: WBdiet: 25% PRO (mainly	HbA _{1C} (%) WB -0.89±0.05 PB -0.6±0.04 CB -0.36±0.04

		parallel-arm clinical trial		<p>PBdiet (42g various PRO sources) CBdiet (high CHO B, 17 g PRO from various sources)</p> <p>PBdiet: 25% PRO (mainly from eggs, tuna, soy), 50% CHO, 25% FAT</p> <p>CBdiet: 11% PRO (soy), 64% CHO, 29% FAT</p> <p>Hypocaloric diets: B 660±25 kcal L 560±20 kcal (23% PRO, 48% CHO, 29% FAT) D 280±15 kcal (31% PRO, 31% CHO, 38% FAT)</p> <p>B at 6:00-8:30h, L at 12:30-14:30h, D at 18:30-20:30h</p>	<p>Fasting Glu (mmol/L) WB -0.73±0.06 PB -0.43±0.06 CB -0.12±0.04</p> <p>Overall glycemia was -12% in PB and -19% in WB Glu peak was -18% in PB and -31% in WB Rapid Glu levels decrease after B in PB and WB Overall AUC_{Ins} was +37% in PB and 62% in WB (same for after L and D) AUC_{C-pept} was +53% in PB and 96% in WB (same for after L and D) AUC_{iGLP-1} was +70% in WB and +33% in PB after B, L, and D HbA_{1C} reduced in all grps</p>
Jakubowicz, <i>et al.</i> , 2012 [152]	20-65 32.3±1.8	32 weeks Randomized, treatment controlled, open clinical trial	144	<p>LCb HCPb</p> <p>Low kcal and low CHO diet (LCb) with low kcal and low HCO B High CHO and high PRO diet (HCPb) with daily dessert for B</p>	<p>BW (kg) 70.6±8.7 (HCPb) vs 86.9±9.7 (LCb) Fasting Glu (mg/dl) 84.2±4.6 (HCPb) vs 95.5±4.9 (LCb) Fasting Ins (µU/ml) 8.9±3.9 (HCPb) vs 23.69±3.8 (LCb) HOMA-IR 1.6±0.4 (HCPb) vs 5.9±0.9 (LCb) Total Chol (mg/dL) 179.2±11.1 (HCPb) vs 190.8±18.2 (LCb) TG (mg/dL) 122.6±9.7 (HCPb) vs 174.5±20.9 (LCb) ↑ hunger in LCb</p>

					Similar L & D composition, differences for B	
Neumann, <i>et al.</i> , 2016 [153]	Healthy 24.1±2 n/a	8 days Randomized, controlled study	24	SKP (Skipping breakfast) CHO PRO	SKP group CHO group: 351 kcal; 59 g CHO, 10 g PRO, 8 g fat PRO group: 350 kcal; 39 g CHO, 30 g PRO, 8 g Fat B consumed as first meal of the day, before 10:00am	No difference in fasting blood Glu CHO and PRO groups lead to greater ppd Glu vs SKP ↓10% Glu in PRO vs CHO at 30min ppd Ffter B
Pedersen, <i>et al.</i> , 2016 [154]	Obese/T2D 63.9±2.15 33±1.25	4 exp. days Randomized crossover study	28	CHO-B noCHO-B	Fast ≥8 h before the test diets The diets were consumed on 2 sequential days on separate weeks 3 identical meals with CHO 3 meals, no CHO breakfast, lunch and dinner with CHO –similar to other group	Peak blood Glu (mmol/L) 11.3±0.5 after CHO-B 9.4±0.4 after noCHO-B Mean blood Glu (mmol/L) – 5h after B 8.4±0.5 after CHO-B 7.5±0.4 after noCHO-B no sig. differences in Glu measurements after lunch and dinner no sig. differences in gastric-emptying
Rabinovitz, <i>et al.</i> ,	Overweight/ obese with T2D	3 months Randomized, treatment-	46	SB (small breakfast)	At B: 12-18% PRO, 14- 22% FAT,	BW no sign. difference HbA1c (%)

2014 [155]	60.7±6.35 32.37±3.7	controlled, open clinical trial		BB (big breakfast)	60-70% CHO, 13% of total E was recommended in the SM, Lunch and Dinner had 33% of total daily E, 2-3 snacks same as in BB At B: 23-30% PRO, 29-37% FAT, 37-48% CHO 33% of total E was recommended in the BB, Lunch and Dinner had 25% of total daily E, 2-3 snacks same as in SM	-0.58±0.18 in BB -0.13±0.08 in SB Estimated average glucose (mg/dl) -16.6±5.2 in BB -3.43±2.4 in SB no sign. changes in Glu, Ins, C-peptide, total Chol, TG, CRP, IL-6, TNF-α
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Abbreviations: B: Breakfast; L: Lunch; D: Dinner; YesB: had breakfast; NoB: skipped breakfast; T2D: type 2 diabetes; ppd: postprandial; GI: Glycemic Index, GL: Glycemic Load; BSD: breakfast skipping day; DSD: dinner skipping day; PRO: protein; CHO: carbohydrates; FAT: fat/lipids; HOMA-IR: homeostatic model assessment for insulin; AUC: area under the curve; iAUC: incremental area under the curve; Ins: insulin concentrations; Glu: glucose concentrations; HbA1c: glycated hemoglobin A1c; ISI: insulin sensitivity index; WB: body weight; E: total energy intake; SKP: skipping breakfast.